

Unravelling of theoretical window to fabricate high performance inorganic perovskite solar cells

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Perovskite solar cells (PSCs) have celebrated a decade of intense investigation as a promising photovoltaic technology, measuring a power conversion efficiency of >25.2% with the use of lead based light harvester. Recently, inorganic cesium cation based mixed halide perovskite ($\text{CsMI}_{3-x}\text{Br}_x$, $M=\text{Pb}$ or Sn) as an absorber in PSCs gave promising results, particularly CsPbI_2Br demonstrated improved thermal stability and carriers transport properties. However, the performance is far-off from the theoretical limit due to intriguing issues such as high defect density (N_t), energetic level mismatch. Such barrier can be overcome through device modelling and unraveling of the kinetics. Here we have employed computational approach to design and investigate efficient inorganic CsPbI_2Br based solar cells by elucidating the role of defect density in the perovskite on the performance, by employing different types of hole transport layers via optimizing their valence band offset and barrier height at back contact. By optimizing such parameters for CsPbI_2Br , the efficiency of 17.71, 17.44 and 17.54 % using CuSCN, PTAA and Spiro-OMeTAD as HTMs respectively can be reached. Furthermore, lead free $\text{CsSnI}_{3-x}\text{Br}_x$ ($0 < x < 3$) based PSCs were simulated and the effect of band gap variation as a result of Br content was studied on the performance. The influence of defect density of the absorber layer ($\text{CsSnI}_2\text{Br}_2$) and at of interfaces was studied and with optimized defect density, $\text{CsSnI}_2\text{Br}_2$ based PSCs gave an efficiency of 20.32 % with V_{oc} of 1.35 V when SnO_2 was used as electron transport layer and Spiro-OMeTAD as HTM. Our simplistic approach suggests way for experimental design protocol to achieve high performance inorganic Pb and Sn based PSCs.

1. Introduction

Solar energy is one of the most promising source of energy to counter the adverse effect of climate change on our planet. Emerging photovoltaic technologies can potentially reach to the masses, in particularly perovskite solar cells (PSCs). The hybrid organic inorganic lead (Pb) based perovskite as a light absorber (APbI_3) is the most investigated in PSCs due to their excellent electro-optical properties¹⁻⁵ and gave record performance.^{6,7} However, hybrid organic-inorganic lead halide perovskite suffers from challenges such as, efficiency,⁸ thermal instability at high temperature, originating due to volatile nature of organic cations (FA or MA).^{9,10} Replacement of the organic cations by inorganic cations such as Cs found to be an effective approach to overcome such bottleneck.^{11,12} However, the CsPbI_3 is stable only in cubic perovskite (α -phase) at high temperature, which can be easily converted to orthorhombic non-perovskite (δ) phase.¹³ In this context, $\text{CsPbI}_{3-x}\text{Br}_x$ evolved as a promising material for new architect of PSCs in term of phase stability. Snaith et al reported CsPbI_2Br is stable in the cubic phase at room temperature with a band gap of 1.82 - 1.92 eV¹⁴, partial substitution of I to Br into CsPbI_3 stabilizes the cubic phase, this led to intense investigation and performance of CsPbI_2Br based PSCs up to 16.07 % was reported.¹⁵ Such results were obtained by reducing the defect density in the active layer, growth control of CsPbI_2Br through optimized annealing temperature¹⁶, using effective anti-solvent approach¹⁷ or minimizing the energy level gap at the charge selective layers,¹⁸ similar to hybrid lead halide PSCs.¹⁹ However, the performance remains lower from the theoretical limit of 22.1 % PCE and 1.65 V_{oc} , when 500 nm thick CsPbI_2Br was used.²⁰ To achieve the theoretical efficiency limit, the strategy should be focus on reducing the defect density of the active layer, and it should

be less than the current value of $3.64 \text{ E}15 \text{ cm}^{-3}$.²¹ The energy alignment at the charge selective layers needs further optimization using p-type conducting polymers or inorganic semiconductors to minimized energy loss ($E_{loss}=E_g - eV_{oc}$, E_g is the band gap and e is the elementary charge). Arguably, the efficient CsPbI_2Br based PSCs should focus on reducing E_{loss} as much as possible by improving V_{oc} and J_{sc} , this target can be achieved through energy alignment and high quality CsPbI_2Br crystal formation. The most efficient CsPbI_2Br based PSCs yielded PCE of 16.79 % with an V_{oc} of 1.32 V, i.e. $E_{loss} = 0.59 \text{ eV}$.²²

The toxicity of the lead (Pb) metal is visualized as a barrier for commercial success of inorganic PSCs. Tin (Sn) as possible metal to replace the problematic Pb is being investigated.²³ Compared to Pb-, Sn-based perovskites showed high optical absorption coefficients,^{24,25} narrow optical band gaps and high charge carrier mobilities.²⁶ In accordance to the perovskite structure, ABX_3 , the A cation can be (MA, FA and Cs), in case of MA cation an efficiency of 6.4% was achieved by using MASnI_3 as light harvester having a band gap of 1.3 eV.²⁷ Further, using FA cation, slightly larger than MA, Koh et al. prepared FASnI_3 with incorporation of 20% SnF_2 addition, a PCE of 2.10% was achieved with a band gap of 1.41eV.²⁸ However, the instability of organic-inorganic halide perovskite is of concern, due to the use of organic cations under outdoor conditions.²⁹ To resolve this stability issue, Cs as A cation was opted for all inorganic Sn-based perovskites with $X = \text{I, Br}$, which has similar electro-optical properties to FASnI_3 and MASnI_3 . The first report using Sn-based all-inorganic PSCs was reported in 2012, where CsSnI_3 acted as hole transporter gave a PCE of 0.9 %.³⁰ However, instability of Sn in the +2 oxidation state, which can be easily converted to the +4 state in the presence of moisture and oxygen³¹ was a limiting factor. To resolve the oxidation issues of Sn, SnCl_2 and SnF_2 as reducing agents was exploited to minimize the extent

of *p*-type self-doping of the perovskite and to reduce the hole carrier density, in order to improve the performance.^{32,33} Besides, mixed anion containing CsSn_{3-x}Br_x as light harvester has been studied, and its band gap was tuned from 1.27 eV to 1.74eV by varying the percentage of Br from *x* = 0–1.³⁴

Although, these Inorganic Sn-based PSCs shows lower performance compared to their Pb based counterparts, but their low band gap exhibits a high potential to exploit them in perovskite-perovskite tandem solar cells. Further, investigation of macroscopic device model of inorganic Sn-based PSCs is still obscure and a lot of issues need to be resolved to improve the Sn-based PSCs, such as prevention of bulk and interface recombination due to tin vacancies, rational designing of charge selective contacts to efficiently extract carriers from perovskite. The issue of high hole carrier density as a result of self *p*-doping can be controlled by SnF₂ addition, which will allow to reduce the defect density from pristine value of 1.1E19 cm⁻³ to 5.7E17 cm⁻³ for CsSn₃. This can be retarded further by substitution of I to Br. Taking this into account, we performed theoretical investigation for CsPbI₂Br and CsSn_{3-x}Br_x based PSCs. Firstly, we focus on CsPbI₂Br by studying the effect of interface engineering at HTL and perovskite interface employing different HTMs such as organic (Spiro-OMeTAD), inorganic (CuSCN) and polymeric (PTAA). Additionally, the influence of defect density of CsPbI₂Br absorber layer on performance was studied. The HTM is a channel to transfer the holes from the active layer to back contact, which should be optimized to make better alignment. Most of the studies in PSCs are focused on optimizing the valence and conduction band offset, which is critical for transport and extraction of charges as the height of energy barrier regulates the contact resistance. However, reports showing the effect of energy band alignment between HTM and back contact are in scarce. We reported how the valence band offset can be optimized to boost the performance of PSCs³⁵ Thus to address the mismatch alignment at perovskite/HTM/back contact, firstly, we have elucidated the impact of valence band maximum (VBM) of HTMs (Spiro-OMeTAD, CuSCN & PTAA) on the performance of CsPbI₂Br solar cells and also on the contact between HTM-Back contact. During this process, we discovered that modulating the *E_v* (by varying the electron affinity) of HTM, leads to an arc shape forms at HTM/back contact which changes its curvature with the variation of *E_v* and that has strong influence on the performance of PSCs. Such optimizations led to an efficiency of 17.73, 17.45 and 17.44% using CuSCN, PTAA and Spiro-OMeTAD as HTMs respectively. Secondly, we ran simulation for lead free Sn-based inorganic PSCs, where the effect of I anion substitution by Br in CsSn₃ absorber was investigated to clarify its impact on the conduction band offset (CBO), i.e., the difference between the conduction band minimum (CBM) energy levels of the ETL and those of the perovskite layer, $\Delta E_c = E_{c_ETL} - E_{c_absorber}$.

To our understanding, there is no theoretical or experimental studies emphasized on lead free inorganic PSCs. The “self-doping” in Sn-based inorganic PSCs allows lowering the trap density and its impact on solar cell performance was studied.

We studied the influence of defect density variation in absorber layer and its interfaces to elucidate the optimum values that can boost the efficiency and computed 20.35 % PCE with a *V_{oc}* of 1.35 V.

2. Theory and Computational details

The simulations were performed using SCAPS 3.3.07 software,¹⁹ based on the Poisson equation(1), and the continuity equations for electrons(2) and holes (3)

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(\epsilon(x) \frac{d\psi}{dx} \right) = q [p(x) - n(x) + N_D^+(x) - N_A^-(x) + p_t(x) - n_t(x)] \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{1}{j} \frac{dj_p}{dx} + R_p(x) - G(x) = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$-\frac{1}{j} \frac{dj_n}{dx} + R_n(x) - G(x) = 0 \quad (3)$$

Here, ϵ denotes the permittivity, q , the charge of electron, ψ , the electrostatic potential, n , the free electrons, p , free holes, n_t and p_t are trapped electrons and holes, N_D^+ and N_A^- are the ionized donor and acceptor-like doping concentrations respectively, R_n and R_p are electrons and holes recombination rate, G is the generation rate, J_n and J_p are, the electron and hole current densities respectively.

The symbols presented in the table 1 and 4 can be described as follows: N_A and N_D denote acceptor and donor densities, ϵ_r is relative permittivity, χ is electron affinity, E_g is the band gap energy, N_t is defect density, μ_n and μ_p are mobility of electron and hole respectively, and. Computational studies were performed on a planar PSCs with an architecture of FTO/SnO₂/interface layer 1(IL1) / inorganic perovskite/interface layer2(IL2)/HTM/Au. The defect type in bulk perovskite is considered neutral with a cross section of electron and hole is 2×10^{-14} cm². The electron and hole thermal velocity was 10⁷cm/s. Gold (Au) was used as the back contact while fluorine doped tin oxide (FTO) as the front contact.

Before detailing the band alignment at HTM-back contact, it is imperative to understand the condition for the formation of the junction between *p*-type semiconductor (HTM) and metal for the flow of holes.³⁶

Fig.1 shows the energy band diagrams for semiconductor-metal interfaces, where ϕ is the work function, ϕ_{sp} and ϕ_m refer to *p*-type semiconductor and metal respectively. E_f is the fermi-energy and χ is the electron affinity. If the metal and semiconductor are brought together, two type of contact can be formed depending on the difference of work function of metal and semiconductor: Schottky and ohmic junction as illustrated in

Fig. 1a-b. The type of interface is a result of the levelling of work functions to balance the chemical potential. When the work function of *p*-type semiconducting HTM (ϕ_{sp}) is higher than that of the metal, (Fig.1a), an energy barrier is formed for holes and Schottky contact is created. On contrary, if the work function of HTM (ϕ_{sp}) is lower than that of the metal (ϕ_m), an ohmic contact will be formed (Fig.1b). To analyze the effect of these two interfacial contacts on the performance of

PSCs, we will vary the valence energy level (E_{V_HTM}) of Spiro-OMeTAD and PTAA as HTMs (by changing the electron affinity) with respect to the

Figure 1: Energy band diagrams for semiconductor-metal interfaces for a) Schottky contact and b) ohmic contact.

valence energy level of the perovskite absorber ($E_{V_absorber}$), and rational interfaces at HTM-metal can be observed. The optimized valence band offset (VBO) of each HTM will be the point where the performance of CsPbI₂Br PSCs is maximized. The valence band offset (VBO) is the difference between the valence band energy of the perovskite layer and those of HTM, $\Delta E_V = E_{V_absorber} - E_{V_HTM}$.

The barrier height between a p-type semiconductor and metal can be given by ($\phi_{Bp} = E_g - q(\phi_m - \chi)$ or $\phi_{Bp} = (q(\phi_m - \chi) - E_g)$); Schottky and ohmic contact respectively.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. All inorganic CsPbI₂Br based PSCs

3.1.1 Performance of CsPbI₂Br based PSCs using different HTMs

Photon absorption leads to the creation of an electron-hole pair in a PSC, the electrons travels to the front side through electron selective layers, while hole selective layers conducts the transfer of holes to the back side. To make this process efficient, the energy levels of the interface layers should be in the equilibrium conditions to maximize charge transfer. For efficient transfer of holes, rational HTM with a suitable energetic level as of CsPbI₂Br absorber layer), and the metallic cathode (Au) as the back contact is a prerequisite. We investigated the effect of tuning of the valence band by studying series of HTMs, Spiro-OMeTAD, PTAA and CuSCN, in a structure FTO/SnO₂/IDL1/CsPbI₂Br/IDL2/HTMs/Au, and the preliminary results are shown in the Table3 .Fig.2a presents

the $J-V$ characteristics of inorganic lead based PSCs with different HTMs

Figure 2 :a) $J-V$ curves of PSCs based on different HTMs using parameters shown in Table 1, b) corresponding energy band diagrams of the CsPbI₂Br based PSCs using HTMs illustrating energy barrier at HTM and gold (back contact), and c) corresponding energy band diagrams for the device structure used in the simulation.

employing the parameters (Table 1) and for Spiro-OMeTAD from Table 2. It can be deduced that the HTMs represents similar J_{sc} of ~ 15.67 mA/cm² which does not influence the external quantum efficiency (EQE) of PSCs, while the fill factor (FF) significantly varies by changing the HTM and reaches to 76.66, 79.01 and 81.94 % for Spiro, PTAA and CuSCN respectively, suggesting favorable interfacial contact at CsPbI₂Br/HTM (Fig.2b) 2b). Our simulated PV results of inorganic PSCs (Table 2) are based on CsPbI₂Br with the same configuration that we have used. We noted that the valence band maximum (E_v) value of -5.30 eV for the CuSCN can deliver the highest PCE of 14.90% in contrast to PTAA (-5.25 eV) of 14.28%, while Spiro-OMeTAD (-5.45 eV) gave slightly lower PCE of 14.09%.

Table 1 : Parameters Used in the SCAPS Simulation of Pb based inorganic PSCs.

Parameter	IL1	CsPbI ₂ Br	IL2	PTAA	CuSCN ¹⁹
Thickness (nm)	10	500	10	150	150
E _g (eV)	1.86 ³⁷	1.86 ³⁷	1.86 ³⁷	2.95 ³⁸	3.6
χ	3.8 ³⁷	3.8 ³⁷	3.8 ³⁷	2.3 ³⁸	1.7
ε _r	8.6	8.6	8.6	3.5 ³⁹	10
N _c (1/cm ³)	2.2E18	2.2E18	2.2E18	2.2E18	2.5E18
N _v (1/cm ³)	1.8E19	1.8E19	1.8E19	1.8E19	1.8E19
μ _n (cm ² /Vs)	200 ⁴⁰	200 ⁴⁰	200 ⁴⁰	1E-4 ⁴¹	100
μ _p (cm ² /Vs)	200	200	200	1E-4	25
N _A (1/cm ³)	--	--	--	-	1E18
N _D (1/cm ³)	1E15	1E15	1E15	1E18	-
N _t (1/cm ³)	3.64E16	3.64E15 ²¹	3.64E16	1E15	1E15

The value of the defect density of CsPbI₂Br is equal to 3.64E15 cm⁻³ which is the finest value²¹ while the work function of back contact is -5.1 eV (Au). The difference in the performance between HTMs, can be related firstly; the effect of VBO and the secondly to the barrier height (φ_{Bp}). We can deduct from Table 3 that the efficient PSCs must have a balanced values between the VBO and φ_{Bp} to facilitate the extraction of the holes from the perovskite layer and also to make an efficient transfer of the holes from the HTM to the load.

Table 2 : Experimental value of PV parameters of reported CsPbI₂Br based PSCs using Spiro-OMeTAD and PTAA as HTM.

HTMs	PCE (%)	V _{oc} (V)	J _{sc} (mA/cm ²)	FF (%)
Spiro ³⁷	13.10	1.21	14.60	74.1
PTAA ⁴²	14.36	1.16	15.56	79.06

Table 3 : Simulated values of the PV parameters for CsPbI₂Br based PSCs in a structure FTO/SnO₂/IDL1/CsPbI₂Br/IDL2/HTMs/Au, using different HTMs and using N_t= 3.64E15 cm⁻³ in absorber layer

HTMs	PCE (%)	V _{oc} (V)	J _{sc} (mA/cm ²)	FF (%)	VBO (eV)	φ _{Bp}
Spiro	14.09	1.17	15.67	76.66	-	-0.35
PTAA	14.28	1.15	15.67	79.01	-	-0.15
CuSCN	14.90	1.16	15.68	81.94	-	-0.2
S-Q limit ⁴³	25.86	1.56	17.99	91.69	-	-

Fig.2a,b represents the corresponding energy band diagrams of simulated PSCs with diverse HTMs. The inset shows the formation of an “arc shape” structure at HTM/back contact with different curvature depending on the energy level of the

valence band for each HTM, and It can acts as a barrier to slow down the movement of holes towards the back contact which in turn increases the recombination rate and thus reducing the open circuit voltage. Schottky contact is dominated for all three HTMs with different level as presented with “arc shaped” (Fig.1a).

3.1.2 Influence of CsPbI₂Br defect density (N_t) on performance of PSCs

The performance of the architect simulated here, is in accordance to the recent reports^{37,42}, but is still far from the theoretical values. Arguably, the optimization of the selective layers will be appropriate, if the active layer is also of high quality (low defect density). The defect density influence the performance of PSCs, thus, we will elucidate the effect of this parameter on the performance of PSCs with different HTMs (Fig.3), using the SRH recombination model as follows⁸ :

$$R_{SRH} = \sigma_{n,p} v_{th} N_t \frac{n_p - n_i^2}{n + p + 2n_i \cos\left(\frac{E_t - E_i}{kT}\right)} \quad (4)$$

Here, σ_n and σ_p are capture cross-section for electrons and holes, v_{th} is thermal velocity, N_t is defect density, n and p are the concentration of electron and hole, n_i is the intrinsic density, E_i is the intrinsic energy level, E_t is the energy level of the trap defect.

Based, on Shockley-Read-Hall recombination formula R_{SRH} is directly proportional to the defect density (N_t) of the absorber layer.^{49,50} Fig.3 depicts the efficiency and the V_{oc} variation as a function of defect density in CsPbI₂Br with different HTMs. Defect density of the absorber layer directly affects the performance of PSCs, which is a limiting factor to achieve the Shockley-Queisser limit.^{51,52}

It can be deduced from Fig.3b that by decreasing the N_t of absorber layer up to a certain value (N_t=1E13 cm⁻³), increases the PCE for all the HTMs studied. The lower defect density resulted into the increased lifetime due to increment in diffusion length (a

Figure 3: Influence of defect density in absorber layer using different HTMs on a) open circuit voltage and b) efficiency

measure of absorber quality) which reduces the rate of recombination in absorber. ³ By comparing the PCE value (Table 3) for high defect density of absorber ($3.64\text{E}15 \text{ cm}^{-3}$) and the optimized defect density ($N_t=1\text{E}13 \text{ cm}^{-3}$) increment in PCE was noted to 16.16, 17.44 and 17.71 % for Spiro-OMeTAD, PTAA and CuSCN respectively (Fig.3a). Similar trend was observed for V_{oc} increase with decreasing N_t until reaching the optimized value of $1\text{E}13 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ (Fig.3b). However, the improvement in V_{oc} was higher in case of CuSCN and PTAA and gave the value of 1.43 and 1.42 V respectively, compared to Spiro-OMeTAD of 1.28 V. In case of Spiro-OMeTAD (Table 3), the VBO is less but the barrier height is large in contrast to other HTMs. Even, by considering the low defect density of the absorber layer ($N_t=1\text{E}13 \text{ cm}^{-3}$, for high quality layers) and low value of VBO, will not allow to reach the theoretical value of V_{oc} in case of Spiro-OMeTAD. However, if the barrier height is low with large VBO, the performance can be near to the Shockley limit as shown for CuSCN and PTAA.

To validate these assumptions, Table 5, depicts the effect of VBO and barrier height. Valence band energy level of Spiro-OMeTAD and PTAA is optimized by varying their electron affinity and keeping it closer, to the VBO and ϕ_{BP} values of CuSCN, which is experimentally achievable (Table 5).

Table 4 : Performance of inorganic PSCs using different HTMs by varying the valence band energy level (E_{v_HTM}) and barrier height (ϕ_{BP}) between the HTM and back contact.

HTMs	E_v (eV)	VBO (E_{v_HTM} - $E_{v_absorber}$) (eV)	ϕ_{BP} (eV)	PCE (%)
Spiro-OMeTAD	-4.7	-0.96	-0.4	9.82
	-5	-0.66	-0.1	14.28
	-5.1	-0.56	0	15.79
	-5.25	-0.41	-0.15	17.57
	-5.4	-0.26	-0.3	16.29
PTAA	-5.55	-0.11	-0.45	14.28
	-4.55	-1.11	-0.55	7.95
	-4.85	-0.81	-0.25	12.03
	-5.15	-0.51	-0.05	16.52
	-5.25	-0.41	-0.15	17.44
	-5.3	-0.36	-0.2	17.36
	-5.4	-0.26	-0.3	16.25

3.1.3 The influence of HTM's valence band on the performance of PSCs

Fig.4 represents the influence of valence band maximum of Spiro and PTAA on the performance of PSCs (a & c) and their corresponding energy band diagrams (b & d). The E_v of the HTM was varied through the simulation by tuning the electron affinity (χ) with respect to the perovskite absorber. When the E_v of the HTM decreases with respect to the E_v of the absorber (-5.66eV), the PCE and the V_{oc} increases. Upon acquiring the value of VBM closer to the work function of back contact ($\phi_{BP} = -5.1 \text{ eV}$), the PCE and the V_{oc} saturates, but when the electron affinity is higher than 2.25 eV and 2.3 eV for Spiro and PTAA and corresponds to the $E_v = -5.25 \text{ eV}$ in both cases (Fig. 4a & c) respectively, the performance dropped suggesting the optimized value of E_v is -5.25 eV when gold is used as back contact.

In the context of interface engineering in optoelectronic devices, we can explain these results in two folds, when the VBM of HTMs affects directly and/or at the same time the VBO and the barrier height (ϕ_{BP}) at HTM-Back contact. It implies that an optimized value of VBO and ϕ_{BP} should be established for each HTM

Figure 4: a) Influence of valence band of Spiro-OMeTAD on the performance of CsPbI₂Br PSCs, b) corresponding energy band diagram, c) effect of valence band of PTAA on the performance of CsPbI₂Br PSCs and d) corresponding energy band diagram.

HTMs	PCE (%)	Voc (V)	Jsc (mA/cm ²)	FF (%)
CuSCN	17.71	1.43	15.90	78.90
PTAA	17.44	1.43	15.69	77.76
Spiro	17.57	1.43	15.69	78.31

Table 5: The performance of the optimized FTO/SnO₂/IDL1/CsPbI₂Br/IDL2/HTMs/Au based on different HTMs, compared to the Shockley-Queisser-limit.

HTMs	PCE (%)	Voc (V)	Jsc (mA/cm ²)	FF (%)
CuSCN	17.71	1.43	15.90	78.90
PTAA	17.44	1.43	15.69	77.76
Spiro	17.57	1.43	15.69	78.31

To further elucidate this, we analyzed the band diagram of devices with different value of E_v for each HTM (Fig.4b,d) By focusing on the area between the HTM and the back contact with the change of the E_v of HTMs, the performance increases with increasing the VBO value until -0.41 eV. This corresponds to the electron affinity of 2.25 and 2.3 eV for Spiro and PTAA respectively and, beyond this optimized values of VBO (corresponds to E_{v_HTM} of -5.25 eV), the drop in performance was noted due to the formation of Schottky barrier ϕ_{Bp} for holes. The value of ϕ_{Bp} was calculated using the equation described in the section 2 and increases with increasing the E_{v_HTM} as illustrated in the inset of (Fig.4.b,d) and Table 5. If the Schottky barrier is greater than -0.15 eV, it will hinder the transfer of the holes to the back contact, which decrease the performance of CsPbI₂Br based PSCs. Table 4the Schottky contact is preferable with -0.15 eV to the barrier height.

illustrates the performance of CsPbI₂Br PSCs with the optimized parameters. $N_t = 1E13$ cm⁻³ for absorber layer, VBO= -0.41 eV and $(\phi_{Bp}) = -0.15$ eV.

3.2 Lead free CsSn_{1-x}Br_x PSCs

3.2.1 Bromide substitution on the performance of CsSn_{1-x}Br_x

It is reported that the addition of SnF₂ (20 mol%) allows to decrease the defect density in CsSnI₃ from $1.1E19$ cm⁻³ to $5E17$ cm⁻³, by influencing the morphology of CsSnI₃.¹⁹ Similarly, in of CsSn_{1-x}Br_x band gap on the PCE and V_{oc} of PSCs. Present work, we have focused on the CsSnI₃ where Iodine was partially replaced by bromide anion, to tune the band gap. The band gap variation was studied on the performance of the CsSn_{1-x}Br_x based PSCs. Fig. 5(b) shows the simulated trend of PCE and V_{oc} as a function of band gap for the planar device structure FTO/SnO₂/CsSn_{1-x}Br_x/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au and using the parameter given in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Corresponding to Br/ (I + Br ratio, (x) ranges from 0–3, the band gap was varied from 1.27 –1.75 eV as shown in Fig.5a. Similar trend was noted for CH₃NH₃PbI₃ and CsSnI₃,^{34,53} experimentally validating our investigation. Fig.5b illustrates that the open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) escalates with the increase in band gap due to increased Br fraction, while PCE starts dropping beyond $x=2$.

Figure 6: Influence of defect density in absorber layer on a) J-V curve, (b) the external quantum efficiency and c) efficiency and fill factor

Figure 7: Influence of defect density at CsSnI₂Br₂/HTM on a) J-V curve, (b) efficiency and fill factor and c) the external quantum efficiency and influence of defect density at ETM/ CsSnI₂Br₂ on d) J-V curve, e) efficiency and fill factor and f) the external quantum efficiencies.

3.2.3. Influence of interface defect density at CsSnI₂Br₂/HTM

The quality and nature of interface at absorber/HTM is paramount to fabricate efficient PSCs, here we have varied the N_t from 10^{17} cm^{-3} to 10^{12} cm^{-3} at CsSnI₂Br₂/HTM interface as shown in Fig.7.a-c. We noted abrupt drop in the performance when $N_t > 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and remains nearly unchanged if $N_t < 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, this enhancement was obtained due to the reduction in defect density at CsSnI₂Br₂/HTM interface. The value of contact resistance is higher, when high

defect density $N_t > 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ is present which also led to lower fill factor (Fig.7.b). However, the J_{sc} change is insignificant to defect density variation that can be manifested from the EQE graph Fig.7.c. Thus, we have selected 10^{15} cm^{-3} as an optimum value for CsSnI₂Br₂/HTM interface which could delivers a PCE = 18.17 %, $V_{oc} = 1.29 \text{ V}$, $J_{sc} = 20.29 \text{ mA/cm}^2$ and $FF = 69.29 \%$.

3.2.4 Influence of interface defect density at ETM/CsSnI₂Br₂

We continue our simulation studies with the optimization of ETM/CsSnI₂Br₂ interface, which can further contribute to

improve the performance of PSCs Fig.7d-f By decreasing the value of N_t , the performance increases linearly, and achieve an optimum value of N_t , beyond this value it saturates. From Fig. 7b, we can set $N_t = 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ as an optimal value for ETM/CsSnBr₂ interface, and using this value, a PCE of 20.35 %, with a V_{oc} of 1.35V, $J_{sc} = 20.30 \text{ mA/cm}^2$ and FF = 74.17 % can be derived. It can be concluded that the defect density at ETM/CsSnBr₂ has a strong effect on the performance, as solar irradiation passes through this interface first, thus at this interface photo-generated carrier concentration is higher than of CsSnBr₂/HTM interface. The high defects density will create more recombination sites and traps thus a higher recombination rate. The investigation of the EQE (Fig.7f) as a function of defect density of ETM/CsSnBr₂ interface further support our hypothesis, decrease of N_t leads to enhanced light absorption in the region of 300-700 nm, contributing to the improved EQE.

Figure 8: Carrier diffusion length as a function of defect density in our modelled inorganic CsSnBr₂ based PSC.

3.2.5. Influence of defect density on diffusion length of CsSnBr₂ absorber

The absorber quality can be determined by the diffusion length for the electron and hole in an absorber layer and can be calculated by using the equation 7-9.

$$L = \sqrt{D\tau} \quad (7), \quad \tau_{n,p} = \frac{1}{\sigma_{n,p}\vartheta_{th}N_t} \quad (8), \quad D = \frac{\mu TK_B}{q} \quad (9)$$

Here L is the diffusion length, $\tau_{n,p}$, the charge carrier life time, σ_n and σ_p are capture cross-section for electrons and holes, ϑ_{th} is thermal velocity, and D is the diffusion coefficient. K_B and μ represent Boltzmann constant and charge carrier mobility, q and T represent the magnitude of charge and temperature in Kelvin.

The equations (7,8 and 9) highlight the direct relation between the defect density (N_t) and lifetime $\tau_{n,p}$, of free charges in bulk perovskite, which control the performance of PSCs.

Fig.8 shows the diffusion length (L) of charge carriers as a function of defect density in CsSnBr₂ this provide ideas about the range of the diffusion length required the interfaces.

As discussed in previous section (3.2.), PSCs based on the *n-i-p* configuration, FTO/SnO₂/CsSnBr₂/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au was optimized through studying the impact of defect density in CsSnBr₂ and at its interfaces. By using the optimum values of defect densities for CsSnBr₂ (10^{12} cm^{-3}), CsSnBr₂/HTM (10^{15}

cm^{-3}) and ETM/CsSnBr₂ (10^{14} cm^{-3}) respectively, we can estimate a value of 278 μm as the diffusion length for the charge carriers in absorber layer, and 27.84 μm , 88.06 μm in case of CsSnBr₂/HTM and ETM/CsSnBr₂ interface layers respectively. Further using these optimum values of N_t , a theoretical value of a PCE =20.32 %, $V_{oc} =1.35 \text{ V}$, $J_{sc} = 20.30 \text{ mA/cm}^2$ and FF 74.17 % can be achieved (Table 7).

Table 6 : The performance of the optimized FTO/SnO₂/IDL1/CsSnBr₂/IDL2/HTMs/Au compared to the Shockley-Queisser-limit.

Condition	PCE (%)	V_{oc} (V)	J_{sc} mA/cm ²	FF (%)
Experimental work ³⁴	0.12	0.311	1.32	41
First model (This work)	0.28	1.07	1.69	15.34
Optimized model (This work)	20.32	1.35	20.30	74.17
Shockley-Queisser-limit ⁴³	29.90	1.37	24.05	90.77

Table 6 summarizes the experimental studies reported and compared to our first model and the optimized model. The optimized model shows promising results in the field of lead-free inorganic PSCs and is in close vicinity of the Shockley-Queisser-limit⁴³. Adopting new experimental protocol for syntheses of tin based materials in Pyrex-tube at high temperature under vacuum can avoid the oxidation and improve the quality (crystallinity) of absorber to harvest more light with low defect density.⁶² Further, the passivation mechanism could be a helpful strategies to minimize the trap density at the interfaces of selective layers.

Conclusions

To summarize, using one dimensional computational approach, device structure of FTO/SnO₂/CsPbI₂Br/HTMs/Au was designed by selecting different organic, polymeric and inorganic types hole transport materials such as Spiro-OMeTAD, PTAA and CuSCN, and the defect density of absorber layer was investigated suggesting significant influence on the performance of PSCs. Tuning the valence band maximum of Spiro-OMeTAD and PTAA demonstrated competitive performance as compared to CuSCN. An optimized value of VBO (-0.41 eV) and the barrier height between the HTM and back contact (-0.15 eV) with schottky contact was found to be beneficial to achieve high performance.

Lead free inorganic PSCs based on CsSnI_{3-x}Br_x was also investigated. The addition of Br to substitute I in CsSnI₃ allows to improve energy level alignment with the ETL. The quality of absorber layer and its interface is paramount to design efficient inorganic Pb-Free PSCs that can be controlled by optimizing defect density. We put forward the design of high performance Pb-Free PSCs having the structure of FTO/SnO₂/CsSnBr₂/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au, with $N_t = 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for absorber layer, and $N_t = 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ in case of CsSnBr₂/HTM and $N_t = 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for ETM/CsSnBr₂ yielding a PCE of 20.32%. Our computational approach can pave the way to boost the

performance of inorganic Pb and Pb-Free PSCs by taking into account developed parameters.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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